

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ETHICAL PRINCIPLES OF A PSYCHOLOGIST AND PSYCHOTHERAPIST

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Abstract

Currently, all social strata of Ukrainian society experience psychological discomfort to varying degrees. This discomfort is mainly aggravated and spreads to ever larger public masses due to the existing harsh realities of the present time, namely such important factors as military actions carried out on the territory of Ukraine and the accompanying worries of Ukrainians for their own lives and health. As well as the life and health of their relatives and friends, and at the same time the future of their homeland in the global political and geographical sense. The lack of social, economic, political stability, and certainty for the present and near future.

At the same time, the level of psychological culture of Ukrainians has increased significantly over the past 10 years.

Thus, the professional demand for highly qualified psychologists and psychotherapists is now great and relevant as never before.

At the same time, the requirements for the level of specialists who take on the responsibility of being healers of souls have also increased significantly.

At the First Constituent Congress of the Society of Psychologists of Ukraine on December 20, 1990 in Kyiv, the Code of Ethics of a Psychologist was adopted. This regulatory act is a guarantor of highly professional, humane, and highly moral activities of psychologists of Ukraine, carried out depending on their specialization and sphere of interests. This Code is a set of ethical norms and rules of conduct that have formed in the psychological community and regulate its life activities. The object of psychologists' research and influence is the inner world of the individual, so their contacts with other people should be warm, friendly, and healing. The Code of Ethics contributes to the more successful implementation of their professional activities by psychologists. In particular, it helps school and university psychologists in increasing the effectiveness of teaching and educating students; psychologists in the field of health care - in performing functions related to the prevention of diseases, treatment, and rehabilitation of patients; psychologists in the field of public administration psychological support of general and sectoral management.

The Ethics Commission established by the Society of Psychologists of Ukraine shall carry out work aimed at the correct interpretation of the Code of Ethics by psychologists, shall monitor its compliance, and shall ensure that psychologists form a perception of this Code as an obligation to the public, as one of the important acts of current legislation

Keywords. ethical principles; psychocorrection; psychotherapy; code of ethics

When considering the terms "psychotherapy" and "psychological correction", it is worth remembering that in psychological and psychological-pedagogical theory and practice they are often used as synonyms. This is due to the fact that the concept of psychotherapy in domestic psychology appeared relatively recently. For a long time, psychotherapy developed as a branch of purely medical care. As for correction, having emerged from the depths of defectology, having gradually passed into age and pedagogical psychology and being actively used in work with children (having acquired the form of "psychological correction"), this term went beyond the scope of child psychology and began to be used in relation to adults when providing them with psychological care. The penetration of the achievements of foreign psychology and its concepts into the context of our science has introduced a certain misunderstanding into the existing terminology. Thus,

in relation to psychological assistance in the non-medical aspect, in domestic psychology the term "correction" was more often used, while in foreign psychology - "psychotherapy". So, since there are two terms, let's try to explore the specifics of each of them and the commonality between them. Where a psychologist works not with abnormal individuals, but with those whose ontogenetic development is within the norm and who need help not in intellectual, but in personal development, the separation of psychotherapy and correction becomes much more complicated. Let's consider two fundamental points: the goals and methods of these types of psychological assistance. The goal of psychotherapy is to create conditions for the full development of the personality, the goal of psychological correction is to eliminate shortcomings in the development of the personality. As can be seen, the tasks of psychological correction have a certain semantic difference, although

they may be subordinate to the psychotherapeutic goal as a more general one. As for methods, psychological correction, unlike psychotherapy, does not have its own special methods, but uses, depending on the needs, methods of psychotherapy, pedagogy, and medicine. Thus, psychological correction approaches psychotherapy and even coincides with it when the implementation of corrective influence helps to realize the psychotherapeutic goal, as well as when it uses exclusively (or predominantly) psychotherapeutic methods of helping a person [8].

In the system of regulation of professional activity, ethical principles play an important role. They establish the rights, responsibilities, and type of relationships of participants in the psychotherapeutic process. In a number of countries around the world, there are codes of ethics for psychologists that determine the activities of professionals (Ethical Principles of Psychologists and Code of Conduct, 2002). Professional duty requires action from a psychologist, practical ethics determines the depth of influence on another person, and the profession dictates the acceptance of restrictions on one's own actions. The issue of professional responsibility of a psychotherapist who carries out a complex of diagnostic, psychotherapeutic, psychoprophylactic, and psychohygienic measures becomes especially relevant due to the increase in the number of psychotherapy offices and the involvement of an increasing number of specialists in this work. In the system of regulation of professional activity, ethical principles play an important role, which establish the rights, responsibilities, and type of relationships of participants in the psychotherapeutic process. [1, p. 37]. Also, in our country, where not everyone even imagines what psychology actually is, a "man from the street" who turns to a psychologist for help does not always understand what kind of help he needs and in what form he can get it. Often, clients' expectations are inadequate, do not correspond to the reality of life and the logic of relationships (for example, as is often the case, a client begins to demand that someone love or lose love for someone as a result of the psychologist's influence, etc.). In this regard, often the first thing a psychologist has to do is explain what psychological help actually consists of and what it should be. From this point of view, psychological counseling, as one that is focused primarily on achieving a specific goal and is not too binding in terms of the nature of the influence, is often a kind of stepping stone, the first step to longer and deeper psychological work [2, p. 28].

The rights of clients who have sought help are not protected by law and there is a complete lack of judicial practice in considering cases of violation of the rights of both participants in the psychotherapeutic process. At the First Constituent Congress of the Society of Psychologists of Ukraine on December 20, 1990 in Kyiv, the Code of Ethics of a Psychologist was adopted. This regulatory act is a guarantor of highly professional, humane, and highly moral activities of psychologists of Ukraine, carried out depending on their specialization and sphere of interests. This Code is a set of ethical norms, rules of conduct that have developed in the psychological community and regulate its life activities. In

this situation, the importance of ethical norms is especially increasing, although they are only of a recommendatory nature. A practical psychologist uses the same methods as a clinical psychotherapist, the difference lies, first of all, in their focus. The most important task of a practical psychologist is not to remove or alleviate symptoms, but to create conditions for optimal functioning of the personality and its development, in particular, in order to improve relationships with other people (family members, colleagues, etc.) [3, p. 7]. Below we will describe the most general principles that ensure compliance with professional ethics in the psychotherapeutic process.

The main ethical principles in the work of a psychologist are:

- Principle of confidentiality
- Principle of competence
- Principle of responsibility
- Principle of ethical and legal competence
- Principle of qualified promotion of psychology
- Principle of client well-being
- Principle of professional cooperation
- Principle of informing the client about the goals

and results of the examination

- Principle of protecting the client's interests

The specified principles are consistent with professional standards adopted in the work of psychologists in the Ukrainian and international community.

Principle of confidentiality. Respecting the client's interests requires keeping everything that happens during the session secret. The psychologist is obliged to observe confidentiality in everything that concerns the relationship with the client, his personal life and life circumstances. Information obtained by the psychologist in the process of conducting work is not subject to conscious or accidental disclosure, and in situations where it is necessary to transfer it to third parties, it must be presented in a form that excludes its use contrary to the interests of the client. The term of confidentiality is not limited. A psychologist should not provide information about the client to any official. The content of the work should not be discussed with parents, even if they initiated the child's request for help. The psychologist does not collect additional information about the client without his consent and is satisfied only with the information that is necessary to perform a professional task. During online work, the psychologist always ensures confidentiality so that the session cannot be seen or heard by outsiders, even by accident. The ethics of the psychologist's professional activities require him to be careful with his records, notes and any other documents related to therapy. And to make sure that no one sees or reads them. The death or disappearance of the subject does not exempt the psychologist from the need to maintain professional secrecy. If the information received from the client is requested by experts or is necessary for scientific purposes, it must be provided in a form that excludes the identification of the client. Reports on professional activities, research results and publications must be prepared in a form that excludes the identification of the client by people not included in the circle of professionals working with this client.

The presence of third parties during diagnosis or consultation requires the prior consent of the client and persons responsible for him (if the client has not reached the age of 16). The administration of the education management body or educational institution, on whose instructions the psychological examination is being conducted, must be warned that it is subject to the obligation of confidentiality. When informing the administration of the results of the examination and his conclusion, the psychologist must refrain from reporting information that is harmful to the client and is not relevant to the educational situation. At the same time, confidentiality has its limits, and the client should be warned about them at the beginning of the work. If the client has reported any information about a possible danger to his life, health, well-being or the lives of other people, the psychotherapist will take measures to prevent it. This may require the intervention of other persons and the disclosure of information. For example, a psychotherapist cannot ignore a message about a planned suicide or a child running away from home. The opportunity to discuss the client's problem with colleagues, primarily with the supervisor, is also communicated at the initial stage of work. Special consideration is required for confidentiality when working in a group. The psychotherapist is responsible for forming such group norms that could create an atmosphere of trust when what is happening in the group does not go beyond its boundaries.

The principle of competence. Only psychologists with higher specialized education are allowed to work with clients. Only a specialist with higher psychological education has the right to provide psychological counseling. A psychologist's diploma is necessary not only because non-specialists do not know and do not understand many things. Over the years of study at the Faculty of Psychology, students develop a special worldview. From the point of view of psychological counseling, it is important that its basis must necessarily be an idea of the complexity and contradictions of the nature of the human psyche and behavior, a conviction in the absence of any everyday norms and dogmas within which the client can be unambiguously assessed. [2, p. 14]. Psychologists constantly update their knowledge of new scientific achievements in their field of activity. A psychologist clearly defines and takes into account the boundaries of his own competence, and undertakes to solve only those tasks that fall within his sphere of competence. If a psychologist feels that he has reached the limit of his competence, he seeks professional support in the form of supervision, that is, he tells about his difficulties to a more experienced colleague, removing all names and details from the story so that the client cannot be identified and supervision does not violate the client's right to confidentiality. In some cases, the ethics of a practicing psychologist reminds him to seek additional personal therapy. The psychologist may refer the client to a colleague or advise him to consult a psychotherapist. The psychologist is responsible for maintaining and developing the level of his professionalism. And for taking on tasks within his competence. For example, not working with psychi-

atric diagnoses without additional education. The psychologist is responsible for choosing the procedure and methods of working with the client.

Principle of responsibility. A psychologist is aware of his professional and personal responsibility to the client and society for his professional activities. When carrying out his work, a psychologist cares, first of all, about the well-being of people and does not use the results of his work to their detriment. The attitude towards the client should be based on accepting the client as he is. Then he becomes able to accept himself. The paradox of this situation is that only by accepting himself is a person able to change. The position of a psychologist is not to assess the severity of sin, not to justify the client, not to give advice, but to help with personal growth. A psychologist has knowledge and experience, but neither education nor experience allows him to make decisions for the client. At the same time, a psychologist can ask questions about different options for the development of the situation, helping the client explore all possibilities. Bias regarding ethnicity, gender, sexual identity, social status, religion is always a gross violation of ethics. A psychologist does not impose his values and does not express his opinion about "how to do it right." In some cases, if fundamental value differences arise, a psychologist may refer a client to another specialist. For example, a psychologist whose family suffered in World War II may refuse to work with a client who denies the Holocaust - this will be ethical.

A psychologist has the right to refuse a patient if his request is unrealistic or may cause harm to the patient, the psychologist or society.

A psychologist is professionally responsible for his own statements on psychological topics in the media, social networks and in public speeches. In public speeches, a psychologist has no right to use unverified information, to mislead people about his education and competence.

A psychologist must refrain from any actions or statements that threaten the integrity of a person. A psychologist has no right to use his knowledge and position to humiliate human dignity, suppress a person or manipulate them.

When making a decision to provide psychological assistance to incapacitated persons (minors; persons in an acute state of stress; patients who have a diagnosis of a mental disorder known to the psychologist at the time of referral, etc.), the psychologist is responsible for the consequences of the intervention chosen and used by him.

First of all, a psychologist must be aware of and be able to solve his own problems, as they provoke errors in work. If a psychologist compensates for his problems, he turns out to be closed to understanding the client and falls into the trap of countertransference. For example, a consultant who does not have early experience of acceptance is always waiting for recognition and will gladly participate in the game of "wonderful doctor". The psychologist is a model for the client, and therefore his condition largely determines the nature of the changes taking place.

The principle of ethical and legal competence. A psychologist can perform his duties as an official expert in accordance with the Legislation of Ukraine. The relationship between a therapist and a client is not friendship, but a professional relationship, with additional restrictions. The ethics of the professional activity of a psychologist (for any areas of psychotherapy) prohibits a specialist from being friends or starting romantic relationships with clients, accepting expensive gifts from them, asking for help, conducting joint business, that is, entering into any "dual relationships" in parallel with therapeutic ones. Dual relationships harm the therapy process and often make effective psychotherapy impossible.

The principle of qualified propaganda of psychology. In any messages intended for people who do not have a psychological education, one should avoid excessive information that reveals the essence of the professional methods of his work. Such information is possible only in messages for specialists. In any messages, the psychologist must depict the possibilities of the methods of practical psychology in accordance with the real state of affairs. One should refrain from any statements that may cause unjustified expectations from the psychologist.

The principle of client well-being. In his professional actions, the psychologist is guided by the well-being of the client. In cases where the psychologist's duties contradict ethical norms, the psychologist resolves these conflicts, guided by the principle of "do no harm."

In the course of professional activity, a psychologist should not allow discrimination (restriction of constitutional rights and freedoms of a person) based on social status, age, gender, nationality, religion, intelligence and any other differences. In the professional activity of an educational psychologist, the rights and interests of the child as the main subject of the educational process are declared priority.

The principle of professional cooperation. The work of a psychologist is based on the right and obligation to show respect for other specialists and their methods of work, regardless of their own theoretical and methodological preferences. The psychologist refrains from assessments and comments on the means and methods of work of colleagues in the presence of clients.

When solving specific tasks of examination, consultation and treatment of people, the psychologist decides whether he can use the knowledge, technical and administrative capabilities of other specialists for the benefit of the client and, with the client's consent, enter into contact with them.

The psychologist assumes professional responsibility for qualified examination, consultation, treatment. The psychologist agrees on the terms of completion of his activities or the advisability of referring the client to another competent specialist. The psychologist is relieved of responsibility if he is convinced that another specialist has taken responsibility for the client.

The principle of informing the client about the goals and results of the examination. The psychologist informs the client about the goals and content of the

psychological work carried out with him, the methods and means used so that the client can decide to participate in this work. Patients cannot be treated against their wishes or without their consent. This is also true for children; in these cases, the consent of their parents or guardians is also required. The rights of the child should not be violated by concluding a contract exclusively with the parents without the consent of the child. When working with patients with severe mental disorders (i.e. in extreme cases), deviations from the principle of voluntariness are allowed, but within the limits of legislative norms. In cases where a psychological procedure is carried out with children under 16 years of age, consent to the child's participation in it must be given by the parents or persons replacing them. In the process of professional activity, the psychologist expresses his own considerations and assesses various aspects of the situation in a form that excludes restrictions on the client's freedom to make an independent decision. In the course of providing psychological assistance, the psychologist must strictly adhere to the principle of voluntariness on the part of the client. The psychologist must inform the participants in psychological work about those aspects of the activity that may affect their decision to participate (or not to participate) in future work: physical risk, discomfort, unpleasant emotional experience, etc. To obtain the client's consent to psychological work with him, the psychologist must use clear terminology and language that is understandable to the client. The conclusion based on the results of the work should not be categorical, it can only be offered to the client as recommendations. Recommendations should be clear and not contain deliberately unattainable conditions. The psychologist does not draw conclusions or give advice without having reliable knowledge about the client or the situation in which he is. The psychologist's conclusion should contain only the necessary and at the same time sufficient information to solve the task, indicate the boundaries of the research carried out, and the nature of the symptoms detected.

Principle of protecting the interests of the client.

By default, video, photo or audio recording of sessions is prohibited. If the therapist believes that the recording is necessary for the progress of therapy, he must explain the therapeutic content of the recording to the client and obtain permission. If the therapist is undergoing training and needs session recordings for certification or obtaining a diploma, the ethical norms of the psychologist require that this be notified in advance, that is, before the start of therapy or the first session.

If the therapist wants to use the information received from the client in the preparation of any materials (case studies, articles, analyses, etc.), he must obtain the client's consent and ensure that the name and known details are changed.

The psychologist does not participate in actions directed against the freedom of the individual, has no right to force the client to talk about his philosophy of life, political, religious or ethical beliefs, has no right to demand that he renounce them.

A psychologist has no material or personal privileges, cannot use his knowledge and position, trust and

dependence of the client in his own selfish interests. In cases where the psychologist's services are paid, the financial conditions are agreed in advance.

A psychologist avoids establishing informal relationships with the client if this may interfere with carrying out diagnostic, consulting and correctional work with him. There should be no sexual intimacy between the psychologist and the client during the period when the psychologist is responsible for him.

Conclusions. Unfortunately, despite the growing number of practicing psychologists, we still cannot say that practical psychology (counseling, psychotherapy) has become a developed field of professional activity. There are several reasons for this:

1) The driving force behind the development of practical psychology in all countries of the world was the open legal private psychological practice – and it still remains in a semi-legal position in our country today.

2) The impetus for the rapid development of any industry, the formation of private practice, is a developed legislative framework – this is something that is not available in Ukraine – the activities of private practical psychologists are not regulated in any way.

3) The professional growth of practical psychologists is facilitated by the introduction of licensing and certification systems at the state level. In reality, none of the psychological associations in Ukraine is recognized by the state as having the right to issue a certificate or license for state-level activities. Only very responsible psychologists try to obtain a certificate from a certain psychological association, which would give them the moral (only moral) right to practice. The majority believes that a higher education diploma, or even just two well-read authors – S. Freud and D. Carnegie – is quite enough. [4; p.278]

Members of international associations try to be guided by the codes of these organizations, but they are difficult to adapt to our reality. For example, the basic requirement for a consultant is to conclude a written agreement with the client on the provision of psychological services [5]. This is done in order to avoid ambiguities in the interpretation of the counseling process and its result. In addition, such a document is evidence in court if the client or psychologist are forced to resolve disputes in this way. What kind of written agreement can we talk about when a psychologist works without registration and a license? It is the signing of this agreement that jeopardizes the possibility of further practice, because in fact it is a crime - the profit from such activities is completely illegal, undeclared, and therefore - illegal. On the part of the client - to which court can he appeal with a complaint about the actions of the consultant, if the Law of Ukraine gives very few answers to these questions [6]. Of course, the connection of professional ethics with the legislation of the country is important for psychology. Since one of the main tasks of the state is the legal protection of human rights and freedoms, it would be quite logical for a citizen to appeal to law enforcement agencies and the court regarding the humiliation of dignity, violation of the boundaries of the inviolability of a person or dam-

age to his mental or physical health as a result of psychological research. The question arises, is there a need to create special ethical commissions and committees, if the problem of unprofessional unethical behavior of a psychologist can and should be legally regulated at the state level? The answer to the question involves studying the problem of the relationship between ethics and law in the field of psychological research.

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